

PEDAGOGICAL PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACH IN THE PRIMARY GRADES OF GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS THROUGH FOLK ARTS

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Annotation: *This article provides a broad overview of the pedagogical psychological approach in the primary grades of general secondary schools through the use of folk arts, and teaches primary school students to apply folk arts in a more simplified way. The effect of teaching on the psychology of students is described.*

Keyword: *Pottery, pottery, shape, rhythm, painting, rosette, stylization, bracelet, pottery, stone carving, carving, knitting, weaving, jewelry, embroidery, embroidery, carpet weaving, felt, basket weaving.*

Folk art has gone through many periods of development. But the content and the essence are enriched only by new creative expressions. In particular, the years of independence have been a period of development. Folk artists appeared on the world stage with their works. For example, more than 1,000 potters work at the Rishtan School of Ceramics. He has participated in a number of exhibitions in Tashkent, Moscow and St. Petersburg. 130 of them are members of the Association of Craftsmen. The art of jewelry has come a long way over the last decade. Forgotten traditions began to be revived. The master jewelers of the Dadamukhamedov dynasty, G.Yuldasheva, R.Mukhametshin, M.Noziirkhanov, Sh.Nizomov, M.Olimov can be included in the list of master jewelers. Modern jewelry - amulets, earrings, etc. During the years of independence, the art of pottery in Uzbekistan has been developing based on ancient traditions. It is worth noting that today's creative teachers are creating in accordance with the existing traditions of local schools. The 1990s marked a new stage in the history of wood carving and painting in Uzbekistan. These schools are mainly Tashkent, Fergana, Bukhara and Khiva. The Tashkent Memorial Square, the Samarkand Imam Bukhari Complex, the Oliy Majlis building, the Amir Temur Museum building, are examples of wood carving and painting. In general, all types of folk arts have regained their beauty and shine during the years of independence. In the centuries-old history of the Uzbek people, folk arts and crafts have been a key part of our cultural heritage. Originating and flourishing in the Uzbek land, the applied arts are world-renowned for their uniqueness and uniqueness. When we think about this stage of development, we see that the origin of Uzbek applied decorative art dates back to the first period of mankind, that is, the period of primitive society. Archaeological excavations in the country testify to the fact that the creation of artifacts by man began in the Stone Age and continues for centuries. We have the material evidence

of the primitive community system - cocktails and hunting weapons, household utensils and ornaments, the remains of human settlements. Underground historical monuments, human and animal remains, paintings and reliefs on snow and basement walls are important sources for studying the history of primitive society. During the Paleolithic period, examples of applied and decorative arts began to spread. Archaeologists are still struggling to gather enough evidence before reaching the final conclusions about the location of the artefacts. As people became more sedentary, observing the laws of nature led to an increase in their sense of symmetry, rhythm, and form. He created a unique art of painting, which is based on the smooth repetition or intermingling of the same elements. Painting became widespread in the New Stone Age (Neolithic), influenced and contributed to the development of decorative and applied arts. Decorating pottery and other items with patterns became widespread. Parallel, spiral and wavy lines, circles form the basis of many patterns of this period. Geometric patterns gradually expanded in content, enriching them with schematic shapes derived from the human, animal, and plant worlds. Its elements continued to reflect the symbolic symbols of the cosmic forces. For example, a socket is a symbol of the sun, a wavy line is a symbol of movement, a symbol of water, and so on. The art of painting has not only served as a decorative function, but also to express the ideological and philosophical concepts of the people. During the Bronze Age, pottery flourished in Central Asia. The advent of pottery made the artwork more elegant and beautiful. The red background found in Chust is notable for its ceramics with black paintings and patterns. Decorative and applied arts also play a leading role in the Iron Age. In addition to geometric patterns, the use of plot compositions in decoration is especially developed. Various decorative arts and crafts, weapons of war, hunting and labor found in the underground and tombs also play an important role in the study of the art and culture of ancient Central Asia. The ceramics are made of bronze, gold, and silver, and the surface of the items used for human consumption is decorated with patterns, embossed images, and sculptures. Some of the objects have life events on them. These factual materials serve to understand the art and culture of the past, the aesthetic and artistic views of the people. Archaeological excavations in Uzbekistan have shown the development of the art of painting in Khorezm, Sughd, Bactria and other regions. Remains of paintings and patterns found in the excavations of the Buddhist temples of Fayoztepa (I-II centuries), Dalvarzintepa (I-II century) in Surkhandarya region are a clear proof of this. The "Amudarya Rich" (Oke Rich), discovered by the upper reaches of the Amu Darya, plays an important role in understanding the artistic life and culture of Central Asia in the IV-VI centuries BC. Among the monuments now housed in the British Museum in London are gold statues, various jugs, bracelets, rings, seals, coins, gold chariots and weapons. Alexander the Great (Alexander the Great) defeated the Achaemenid Empire in the 4th century BC and conquered much of Central Asia. Only the nomadic tribes of Khorezm, Fergana and Syrdarya retained their independence. As a result of such a deep philosophical approach to applied art, the creation of works of art based on conditionality, stylization and symbolism has intensified. This historical factor has given impetus to the rapid development of the Uzbek national decorative art, and today our world-famous architectural monuments testify to the wonderful harmony and integration of pottery, tile,

painting, calligraphy, stone carving and other arts. Folk applied decorative art not only enriches the spiritual world of students, forms their artistic taste, nurtures their psyche. Therefore, the Uzbek folk applied art is one of the most important sources for the artistic and moral, universal education of students, the formation of their scientific outlook, as well as raising their cultural level. In the recent past, the most developed types of Uzbek applied decorative art, such as painting, pottery, stone and bone carving, carving, knitting, weaving, jewelry, embroidery, gold embroidery, carpet weaving, felt, basket weaving unique performance technologies, real national names, their specific terms, schools, styles specific to these arts, and the services of renowned masters in these fields are known all over the world. Central Asian painting has long been known around the world. The magnificent buildings built by our ancestors in the past have not lost their charm to this day. These magnificent buildings give the younger generation a great deal of knowledge and ingenuity. The pattern is an Arabic image, meaning a flower, which is an ornament created from the repetition of birds, animals, flora, geometric and other shapes in a certain order. painting flourished and the Arabic script was mastered. The result is an epigraphic style with patterns. The Arabic inscription was drawn along with the patterns. The Arabic script served as both an ornament and a prayer spell. Painting as an art form has long been an important part of Uzbek culture. Over the centuries, his artistic traditions have emerged and developed. Unlike all other types of art, the patterns show the interdependence of generations, the continuity of national traditions. The tradition of painting as a method of studying this type of art has been passed down from grandfather to father and from father to son. Due to this continuation, the art of painting is still preserved. Today, we can take the example of many young people, ie students. The best examples of the pattern are distinguished by the expediency and beauty of the forms, combined through a rich creative imagination. This reflects the difference in the views of folk masters on the environment. The game of drawing in the pattern, like the melody in the music, the song and the fairy tale, consists of "a great generalization of the life experience of the people." Artistic painting is the art of creating beauty in a combination of colors and unique compositions. In his work, the artist skillfully uses the natural luster and harmony of colors, graceful shapes, textures of materials to achieve a bright expression. Applied art enriches and develops students 'aesthetic taste, worldview, deep thinking, imagination and expands students' positive perception of our national heritage. In the traditional architecture of Uzbekistan, painting is mainly used to decorate ceilings, silent arches, palace pillars, mosques, schools, houses of the rich, wooden items. The rhythmic movement of intertwined twigs, branches and luxuriously depicted flowers in delicate floral-geometric patterns, the Islamic motifs in the works of Uzbek masters and the classical motifs of girikh patterns are adapted to the shape of the ceilings. The pattern serves to decorate more interiors and covered porches and porches. Today, these methods are used in architecture. When students look at the ornate ceilings of architectural buildings built in this national style, you can see the deep breath and excitement in the eyes of these students. his has a positive effect on the psychology of students in all respects, not only instills in students self-confidence and, at the same time, the spirit of

humanity and patriotism, but also the feeling of further development and continuation of the heritage of our ancestors. breaks them.

In our country, the successful solution of the problem of science, technology, culture of child rearing, especially the development of perception of space through the senses of existence, has an emotional and aesthetic impact on the minds and emotions of students through existence and art. Put the show on the agenda. Aesthetic education of students is related to their development. Fine arts classes shape students' attitudes towards life and art.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

- 1.S.S.Bulatov, P. P. Shabaratov “NAQQOSHLIK” IQTISODIYOT MOLIYA 2010
- 2.S.S.Bulatov, K.M.G`ulomov “AMALIY SAN`AT” darslik Toshkent “Iqtisod moliya “ 2014
- 3.K. M.G`ulomov “Amaliy san`at “ Toshkent 2007 textbook.
4. S.S.Bulatov “ O`ZBEKISTON XALQ AMALIY BEZAK SAN`ATI” Toshkent 1991
5. Internet materials:
www.ziyonet.uz
arxiv.uz
www.pedagog.uz